

RESEARCH ARTICLE ↓

Effect of Culture on Entrepreneurial Development in South East Nigeria*Authors*

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of Culture on Entrepreneurial Development in South East Nigeria. Specifically, the study adopted the inheritance system and trade apprenticeship as the independent variables while entrepreneurship innovativeness and competitive aggressiveness serve as the dependent variables. The study used a descriptive research design and adopts primary sources of data, the data were collected using a well-structured questionnaire. The data were organized, presented, and analyzed using ANOVA and put in tables, simple percentages while the hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics. The resulting review that the inheritance system has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurial development with a value of ($\beta = 0.854$, $t\text{-cal} = 30.798$, $p = 0.000$). While Trade apprenticeship also has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurship development with a value of ($\beta = .918$, $t\text{-cal} = 36.318$, $p = 0.000$) in South East Nigeria. We concluded that there is a positive and significant effect of culture on Entrepreneurial Development in South East Nigeria. The government should partner with private organizations for a public-private-partnership (PPP) arrangement to create more modern apprenticeship schemes suited for the 21st-century economy.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Development; Apprenticeship Schemes; Entrepreneurship Innovativeness; Competitive Aggressiveness; South East Nigeria

Introduction

Hofstede (2019) defines culture as a collective programming of the mind which distinguishes the members of one group or category of people from others. Terpstra and David (2020) describe culture as a learned, shared, compelling interrelated set of symbols, whose meanings provide a set of orientations for members of a society. Society and culture have an impact on every aspect of business. According to Morrison, Rimmington, and Williams (1999), culture substantially determines attitudes toward entrepreneurship. Culture encompasses motives that initiate and trigger entrepreneurship. The term entrepreneurial development has been defined as the ability to identify business opportunities, the ability to be able to harness the necessary resources to use opportunities identified, and the ability and willingness to initiate and sustain appropriate actions toward the actualization of a business objectives campaign (Worman, 2016). Entrepreneur development takes place within a framework of forces that constitute the system environment, which is either external or internal. A critical issue in entrepreneurial development and growth is firms' ability to adapt their strategies to a rapidly changing system environment in which the entrepreneurs' role is critical to the success or failure of such a firm. For the entrepreneur to be successful, he must be able to identify and find a useful niche within the large environment where it takes a risk, makes strategic business plans, and takes/implements decisions. Marysol, Rosa, and Alexander (2017) noted that the cultural dimensions traditionally related to entrepreneurial activity and entrepreneurship include power distance and institutional collectivism. Power distances defined as the degree to which members of a society expect the power to be shared unequally. Mitchell, Smith, Sewright, and Morse (2000), suggest that a high-power distance hurts business creation processes. According to Shane (1993), this argument is based on the fact that in these societies, individuals of lower social class may consider entrepreneurship as a unique process for individuals of high social class, as the latter would have the necessary resources at their disposal and experience required as a result. In this way, a high proportion of population outside this small group could fail to carry out entrepreneurship in the exercise of assessment of opportunities within the context. Kreiser, Marino, Dickson and Weaver (2010) posit that previous research found that entrepreneurs in cultures with low power distance will have more autonomy and negotiate with less hierarchical bureaucracy, so they are more involved in the behavior of taking risks than those in cultures with high power distance. It is against this background that this research work seeks to investigate the effect of culture on entrepreneurial development in South East Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The socio-cultural factors constitute the structure of society which plays a crucial role in the practice of entrepreneurship. The emphasis on analysis and evaluation of the socio-cultural elements is prompted by the fact that these factors such as cultural values/norms and peer groups, influence directly the behaviour and actions of people about going into business and even the extent to which consumers respond to new products in the market. A careful observation of the business start-ups of most of the worthy pioneering entrepreneurs in South Eastern Nigeria who have passed on; shows sadly that those once thriving business empires died also with their founders. Few examples of such moribund companies include: Ekenedilichukwu Transport Company, Izuchukwu Transport Company, Umeano group, Olympic drinks, Reno drinks, Jimbaz, C to C transport company and a host of others. This unfortunate trend is not only worrisome but begging answers to the questions of what went wrong, and why their children could not salvage the businesses or even grow them further as are the cases with family-owned businesses in America, Europe, and other parts of the world. The inability of most budding entrepreneurs to draw a line between inheritance and innovation has become a daunting challenge. Also, the effect of the trade apprenticeship system on the competitive aggressiveness of many business start-ups has not been fully ascertained. Since culture plays a great role in entrepreneurial development and bearing in mind that no such study has been conducted in this geo-political zone before, the researcher seeks to investigate the effect of Culture on Entrepreneurial Development in South East Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to examine the effect of Culture on Entrepreneurial Development in South East Nigeria. For the study, the following objectives were examined:

- I. To examine the effect of the inheritance system on entrepreneurship innovativeness in South East Nigeria.
- II. To examine the effect of trade apprenticeship on competitive aggressiveness of entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria.

Hypotheses

In an attempt to answer the research questions and to achieve the purpose of the study, the following hypotheses were stated in their alternate form:

- I. The inheritance system has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurship development in South East Nigeria.
- II. Trade apprenticeship has a positive and significant effect on the competitive aggressiveness of entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Culture

Culture is considered to be the underlying values that direct how people behave (Kirton & Greene, 2019). Cultural diversity in the workplace is a result of practices, values, traditions, or beliefs of employees based on race, age, ethnicity, religion, or gender. Economic globalization is one of the driving forces of cultural diversity in the workplace. According to the definition by House, Javidan et al. (2001, p. 494), culture is defined as 'shared motives values, beliefs, identities, and interpretations or meaning of significant events that result from common experiences of members of collectives and are transmitted across age generations. In general, culture is considered as the accepted behaviors, customs, and values of a given society (Dlabay and Scott, 2011). Many components can be considered as elements of culture. These elements arise and are related to the beliefs and behaviour of people. Culture has been defined in different ways. In Anthropology Kluckhohn (1951) views culture as consisting of patterns of thinking, feeling and reaction, acquired and transmitted mainly by symbols, constituting the distinctive achievements of human groups, including how to make the products. For him, the essential core of culture consists of traditional ideas and associated values. Also, an anthropologist, Clifford Geertz (1973) conceptualized culture as the sets of control mechanisms, plans, recipes, symbols, rules, and constructions. Hofstede (1980) defines culture as the collective programming of the mind distinguishing members of a group or category of people from others, where the "category" can refer to nations and regions within or between nations, ethnic groups, religions, occupations, organizations or genres. Thus, George and Zahra (2002), posit that culture is used to refer to the set of values of a nation, a region or an organization, and culture shares and strengthens social institutions, which over time, these institutions, reinforce cultural values.

Inheritance System

Inheritance is the practice of passing on private property, titles, debts, entitlements, privileges, rights, and obligations upon the death of an individual. The rules of inheritance differ among societies and have changed over time. The passing on of private property and/or debts can be done by a notary. The inheritance may be either under the terms of a will or by intestate laws if the deceased had no will. However, the will must comply with the laws of the jurisdiction at the time it was created or it will be declared invalid (for example, some states do not recognise holographic wills as valid, or only in specific circumstances) and the intestate laws then apply. A person does not become an heir before the death of the deceased, since the exact identity of the persons entitled to inherit is determined only then. Members of ruling or royal class who are expected to become heirs are called heirs apparent if first in line and incapable of being displaced from inheriting by another claim; otherwise, they are heirs presumptive. There is a further concept of joint inheritance, pending renunciation by all but one, which is called coparent. Any system of inheritance promotes the continuity of family and societal structures over generations.

Trade Apprenticeship

Apprenticeship is a system for training a new generation of practitioners of a trade or profession with on-the-job training and often some accompanying study (classroom work and reading) (Imberti, 2017). Apprenticeships can also enable practitioners to gain a license to practice in a regulated occupation. Most of their training is done while working for an employer who helps the apprentices learn their trade or profession, in exchange for their continued labour for an agreed period after they have achieved measurable competencies. Apprenticeship lengths vary significantly across sectors, professions, roles and cultures. In some cases, people who successfully complete an apprenticeship can reach the "journeyman" or professional certification level of competence. In other cases, they can be offered a permanent job at the company that provided the placement. Although the formal boundaries and terminology of the apprentice/journeyman/master system often do not extend outside guilds and trade unions, the concept of on-the-job training leading to competence over a period of years is found in any field of skilled labour.

Entrepreneurship Development

Entrepreneurship is derived from the term entrepreneur. According to Rumball (1989), in 1730, the French economist Richard Cantillon described the entrepreneur as an individual who identifies opportunities and takes risks. Schumpeter (1934) suggests that an entrepreneur is an individual who tends to break the balance of the market by introducing innovation within the system. Some use a broader definition such as the creation of new companies. Harper (1996) argues that entrepreneurship is the main force of the economy and sees entrepreneurship as an activity search of profits aimed at identifying and solving specific problems in structurally complex and uncertain situations. According to Sheffield (1988), over time the definition of entrepreneurship has expanded to include economic classification, management style and/or personal attitude. Low (2001) defines entrepreneurship as the process of identifying, evaluating and capturing an opportunity. Moreover, George and Zahra (2002) define entrepreneurship as the acts and processes by which societies, regions, organizations or individuals identify and continue business opportunities to generate wealth. Katz and Green (2009), define the entrepreneur as a person who owns and initiates an organization focusing on "earnings and growth" and shows a tendency to "innovative behaviour". According to Mbaegbu and Ekienabor (2018), it came into use during Middle Ages and was used to describe a person playing varied roles. An entrepreneur was the organizer of production, the risk taker in investment, and the commercialization of inventions. Kent, Sexton, and Vesper (1983), also ascribed the management functions of organizing, coordination, and supervising production as part of the work of the entrepreneur. Schumpeter (1934) later added innovation as one of the many-sided functions of the entrepreneur and described innovation as the discovery of new methods of combining factors of production or perfection of an old method, introduction of new goods and services, opening of new markets and developing a new source of supply of raw materials. There is a litany of conceptualizations of the Entrepreneur. Meredith, Nelson, & Neck (1996), summarise it all by defining the entrepreneur as any person who can see and evaluate business opportunities and take advantage of them even if it means relocating his place of abode to actualize his mission and profit from the venture. Entrepreneurship encompasses all the functions: creating an enterprise by innovation or penetrating a new market segment to make a profit.

Entrepreneurship Innovativeness

An entrepreneur is an innovator or someone who discovers certain technologies that are associated with financial gain (Runyan et al., 2008). Innovativeness is an important component of organizations seeking new opportunities. Rodan and Galunic (2004) show that an important network structure, for heterogeneous access to knowledge, is equally important for overall managerial performance and more importantly for innovation performance. For Santos (2010), innovativeness has two main dimensions, perfectly differentiated, product process innovation and management innovation. The dimensions of human resources (knowledge formation and creation, innovative behavior, and incentives for innovation) affect differently each type of innovation power capacity. Akgün et al. (2007) found that the level of the company's emotional capabilities influences the company's learning capabilities. The company's emotional ability influences its product innovation through learning abilities.

Competitive Aggressiveness

Competitive aggressiveness reflects the organization’s ability to act aggressively in dealing with its competitors. The aggressive dimension in competition reflects the company’s ability to take aggressive actions in dealing with its competitors by increasing product quality, production capacity, and others to attract consumer-buying interest. Iyer and Doucette (2003) state that the environment acts as a moderator for the entrepreneurial performance-orientation relationship through contingent effects. Entrepreneurial orientation is a strong contributor to business performance. Abdullahi et al. (2019) found that competitive aggressiveness has a positive impact on financial performance. Therefore, companies must adopt and encourage a competitive, aggressive approach in decision-making to improve business performance and maintain relevance in the construction industry. For Adeiza et al. (2016), the personality characteristics, such as competitive skills and the level of control possessed by business owners, play a role in business success and entrepreneur satisfaction. Valeria (2013) states that competitive advantage can be achieved through entrepreneurial orientation, environmental adaptability, innovation, and creativity, where the competitive advantage generated by a company can improve business performance.

Source: Researcher’s Compilation, 2022

Theoretical Review: This study is anchored on the following theory

Institutional Economic Theory

The objective of this theory is to establish and analyze the effect of culture on behavior and in this case the effect of culture on entrepreneurial activity. Hofstede, (1980), notes that this theory roots largely in psychological literature, and assumes that culture has a direct manifestation in the behavior of people belonging to a specific culture. It influences the personal values and behavior of individuals. According to Hayton, George, and Zahra (2002), national culture can support or prevent corporate behavior at the individual level. From this perspective, a culture that supports entrepreneurship allows more people to exercise entrepreneurial potential, and in turn, increases business activity. Thus, we can explain the effect of culture on the entrepreneurial success of the South Eastern people of Nigeria based on this theory. In their view, Chinwuba and Ezeugwu (2017) opine that the entrepreneurial worldview of the South Eastern people of Nigeria, which is the pervasive unified socio-economic picture of their cosmos is the main catalyst behind their socio-economic rhythms in the universe. Uchegara (2009) as well affirms that the quest to establish an enterprise is mostly determined by the worldview/culture of the individual. A key aspect of this worldview is the culture of adoration and honor for persons who by hard work have accumulated wealth. According to Oguejiofor (2009), this tradition of encomium is discernible even in the religious beliefs, rites, rituals, festivals, folklores, and myths of the people of the South East geo-political zone of Nigeria. The people see wealth as a means of gaining social prestige and acquiring social befitting rank.

Empirical Review:

Godwin (2020) examined the effects of socio-cultural factors on entrepreneurial performance in selected small-scale business organizations in Bori-Ogoni. The study used Spearman Rank order Correlation Coefficient (Rho) to analyze the collected data and the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was used to test the hypotheses. The result showed that cultural values/norms influence the profitability of selected small scale business organizations in Bori-Ogoni. Onyechi, Ellis, Cosmas & Sussan (2019) examined the assessment of cultural influences on entrepreneurial activities of small manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study adopted the survey method with emphasis on small manufacturing firms in Nnewi. 98 manufacturing firms were sampled. The study results agreed that cultural influences affect SME's/entrepreneur's ability to succeed and survive. But as a note of warning, the significance of the relationship between factors of entrepreneurial success and the cultural environment should be applied with caution. Yereka (2019) examined the influence of culture on entrepreneurial activities in Ogoni land in Rivers State. Cultural values such power distance, individualism, masculinity and uncertainty avoidance were employed as the explanatory variables while entrepreneurial activities were employed as dependent variable. The study adopted survey research design. The population of the study comprise of all the entrepreneurs in Ogoni land. Sample size of four hundred respondents was selected for the study using Taro Yamane formula. The data generated were analysed using frequency, percentage analysis, descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and multiple regression analysis. The study found that individualism, masculinity and uncertainty avoidance recorded a positive and significant influence on entrepreneurial activities in Ogoni Land.

Madichie, Nkamnebe and Idemobi (2018) examined the cultural determinants of entrepreneurial emergence in a typical sub-Sahara African context. The study found that culture had a strong and positive impact on the entrepreneurial and managerial performance of the Nnewi people. The critical aspects of the Nnewi cultural traits that propel entrepreneurial zeal and managerial performance include prudence, individualism, innovativeness, trust, intimacy and openness in the workplace, submissive apprenticeship as well as perseverance. Okwurume and Onuoha (2021) investigated the relationship between cultural diversity management strategies and the organizational performance of multinational firms in Rivers State. The study, using Spearman's rank order correlation coefficient tested the relationship between the dimensions of cultural diversity management – investiture, assimilation, and divestiture; and the measure of organizational performance – creativity. The result revealed significant relationships. Thus, the practice of investiture, assimilation, and divestiture enhances the relationship between workers within the organization and also affords them sound supportive grounds upon which they become more aware and can improve the overall performance of multinational companies in Rivers State. Hana, Monika, and Adéla (2021) examined Diversity Management as a Tool for the Sustainability of Competitive Advantage. The results were obtained through primary analysis via a questionnaire survey at 549 Czech companies. The results indicate that there is a statistical dependence between the application of diversity management and the commercial sector in which the organization operates and the size of the organization. Shakeel and Fazal (2019) explored the possible effect of workplace diversity on employees' performance at Allama Iqbal Open University.

The sample of the study comprised 105 Heads of departments and 545 regular (BPS-2 to15), contractual, daily wagers, and laborers' employees working in AIOU's main campus as well as regional campuses. A stratified random sampling scheme was applied to select the participants. Data was collected through a questionnaire. Pearson correlation test and Regression Analysis test were applied to extract the results. The results revealed that age diversity; gender diversity and ethnic diversity have a negative relationship with the performance of the employees. Experience diversity has a positive effect on employees' performance. Folakemi (2018) investigated the effects of diversity management and inclusion on organizational outcomes (job satisfaction and job performance) among Shell Corporation employees. A cross-sectional research design was adopted. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), convergent and divergent validity, correlational analysis, and structural equation model were used for the analysis. The findings showed a positive effect of diversity management and inclusion on employees' job satisfaction and employees' job performance. Daniel (2019) examined culture as a fundamental factor in the entrepreneurial success of the Igbo people. Using a qualitative and descriptive method of analysis to analyze the data presented, the study reveals that entrepreneurial activities in Igbo land are not a product of Western civilization and colonialism but of the Igbo cultural values and world views. Diaka & Tsetim (2017) assessed Entrepreneurship development and socio-cultural factors among the Tiv People of Benue State, Nigeria. The researcher also examined the effect of the family system, cultural values, and festivities on the development of entrepreneurship and the emergence of entrepreneurs

in Tiv land. The findings of this study indicated that the family system, cultural values, and festivities have a significant effect on the development of entrepreneurship in the Tiv land of Benue State.

Methodology

This study used a descriptive research design to enable the researcher to determine the nature of prevailing conditions without manipulating the subjects. primary sources were the employees of selected small-scale enterprises in the South East of Nigeria and data was collected using structured questionnaires. The structured questionnaire consists of various items based on the five (5) research questions formulated to guide the study was used. All items on the questionnaire were scored based on five (5) points using the Likert Scale developed by Professor Rensis Likert (1908-1981) – (a) Strongly agree, (b) agree, (c) undecided, (d) disagree, and (e) strongly disagree. The population of the study comprises 750 enterprises in southeast Nigeria. The sample was considered based on the strength of the workers. In determining the sample size, the researcher used Taro Yamene’s Statistical Tool for obtaining the sample size from a given population. The allocation of the sample size is obtained using Bowley’s proportional allocation formula. The data were organized, presented, and analyzed (SPSS output 2022) in tables and simple percentages. The research hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics.

The test statistic is calculated as $t = \frac{\bar{X} - \mu}{s/\sqrt{n}}$; Where \bar{X} = Sample Mean, s^2 = Sample Variance, μ = Population Mean, $t =$ Student t-test, With $n-2$ degree of freedom and 0.05(5%) level of significance. **Confidence Level/Level of significance:** Level of significance = α at 5% = $0.05/2$ tailed = 0.025

Data Presentation

Table 1: Questionnaire Distribution and Responses according to the Organization

<i>Business Enterprise</i>	<i>No. of Questionnaire Distributed</i>	<i>No. of Questionnaire Returned</i>	<i>Percentage of Ques. Returned (%)</i>	<i>Questionnaire not Returned</i>	<i>% not returned</i>
ABIA	191	171	47.5	20	3.1
ANAMBRA	67	62	17.2	5	0.6
EBONYI	10	10	2.8	0	0
ENUGU	61	56	15.6	5	0.8
IMO	48	41	11.4	7	1.1
Total	380	340	94.5	20	5.6

Source: Field survey 2022

Table 1 above represents the questionnaire distributed and response rate; 380 questionnaires were distributed to business enterprises in South East Nigeria namely: Abia State, Anambra State, Ebonyi State, and Enugu State. A total number of 182 copies of the questionnaire were administered to business enterprises in Abia State after which 171(48%) were returned and 11(3%) of the questionnaires were not returned; A total number of 64 questionnaires were administered to business enterprises in Anambra after which 62(12%) of the questionnaires were returned and 2(0.6%) of the questionnaires were not returned. A total of 10 questionnaires were distributed to business enterprises in Ebony State after which all of the questionnaires were dully filled and returned. A total number of 59 questionnaires were administered to business enterprises in Enugu State after which 56(16%) of the questionnaires were returned and 3(0.8%) of the questionnaires were not returned. A total of 45 questionnaires were distributed to business enterprises in Imo State after which 41(11%) of the questionnaires were dully filled and returned and 4(1.1%) of the questionnaires were not returned. The researcher, therefore, used the returned 340 copies of questionnaires for the analysis.

Part B: Analysis of Culture and Entrepreneurial Development.

Research Question One: To what extent does the inheritance system affect entrepreneurship development in South East Nigeria?

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

S/N	Inheritance system	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	As an entrepreneur inheritance has given me an extra sense of purpose and pride - and a competitive edge for my business	340	1.00	5.00	4.3509	.84019
2	Inheriting a business has not only helped families but also both the local and global economies.	340	1.00	5.00	4.4038	.76820
3	In business inheritance, there is generally longevity in leadership, which ensures overall stability within a family-run business.	340	1.00	5.00	4.3358	.86408
4	Family firms tend to have a greater sense of commitment and accountability at their heart than non-family firms	340	1.00	5.00	4.3774	.82633
5	A longer-term perspective is a good way to foster a culture of clear strategy and decision-making throughout the businesses inherited from family.	340	1.00	5.00	4.4415	.71601
	Valid N (listwise)	340				

Source: *Field survey 2022*

Data presented in Table 2 shows mean and standard deviation analysis of the relationship among variables. “As an entrepreneur inheritance has given me an extra sense of purpose and pride - and a competitive edge for my business”; 4.3509 (sd = .84019). For “Inheriting a business has not only helped families but also for both the local and global economies; 4.4038 (sd = .76820) for “In business inheritance, there is generally longevity in leadership, which ensures overall stability within a family-run business”; 4.3358 (sd = .86408). For “Family firms tend to have a greater sense of commitment and accountability at their heart than non-family firms”; 4.3774 (sd = .82633). For “A longer-term perspective is a good way to foster a culture of clear strategy and decision-making throughout the businesses inherited from family”. All the items have 4 points which fall under the response rate “Agreed” showing that all the items are accepted that inheritance system affects entrepreneurship development in South East Nigeria.

Research Question Two: To what extent does trade apprenticeship affect entrepreneurship development in South East Nigeria?

Table 3 Descriptive Statistics						
S/N	Trade Apprenticeship	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Apprenticeship is a tried-and-true method of recruiting and maintaining talent	340	1.00	5.00	4.3434	.77789
2	Learning-while-doing method boosts an entrepreneur's confidence to perform quickly and effectively with certainty about his/her capabilities.	340	1.00	5.00	4.4415	.71601
3	Apprenticeships enable entrepreneurs to start working and earn a decent, living wage while learning key skills and gaining the qualifications that future employers want.	340	1.00	5.00	4.4302	.81408
4	Apprenticeships provide you with the benefit of a varied learning environment that promotes hands-on learning.	340	1.00	5.00	4.4038	.78286
5	Rather than sitting in a classroom all day, an apprenticeship gives you the immediate opportunity to apply your knowledge and use your skills in daily practice.	340	1.00	5.00	4.3774	.82633
	Valid N (listwise)	340				

Source: Field survey 2022

Data presented in Table 3 show means and standard deviations analysis of the causative effect: mean scores of 4.3434 (sd = .77789) for “Apprenticeship is a tried and true method of recruiting and maintaining talent”; 4.4415 (sd = .71601), for “Learning-while-doing method boosts entrepreneur’s confidence to perform quickly and effectively with certainty about his/her capabilities.”; 4.4302 (sd = .81408) for “Apprenticeship enable entrepreneur start working and earn a decent, living wage while learning key skills and gain the qualifications that future employers want”; 4.4038 (sd = .78286) for “Apprenticeships provide you with the benefit of a varied learning environment that promotes hands-on learning”; All the items have 4 points which fall under the response rate of “Agreed” showing that all the items are accepted that trade apprenticeship affects entrepreneurship development in South East Nigeria.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One:

H₀₁: The inheritance system has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurship development in South East Nigeria.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error in the Estimate		
1	.885 ^a	.783	.782	.31783		
Predictors: (Constant), Inheritance						
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	95.816	1	95.816	948.533	.000 ^b
	Residual	26.567	118	.101		
	Total	122.383	119			
Dependent Variable: Entrepreneurial Development						
Predictors: (Constant), Inheritance						
Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.560	.122		4.578	.000
	INHERITANCE	.854	.028	.885	30.798	.000
a. Dependent Variable: ENTREPRENEURIAL DEVELOPMENT						

Source: SPSS output 2022

The R² (Coefficient of determination):

In the above model, R² = 0.783 adjusted to 0.782, which implies that approximately 78% of the variation in the dependent variable “Entrepreneurial Development” is caused by the explanatory variable “Inheritance System” (INHERITANCE).

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

The F-test, which follows an F-distribution, measures the overall significance of the model. From the above result, F-Statistics was recorded (948.533; p = 0.000) which implies that the Inheritance system has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurial development in South East Nigeria.

Student’s T-Test:

This test was conducted to ascertain the significant status of each of the parameters or variables. In doing this, we employed the two-tail tests which compared the t-calculated for the explanatory variables with the t-tabulated. The results presented in Table 4 showed an “Inheritance System’ ($\beta = 0.854$, t-cal =30.798, p = 0.000). From the analysis, we also conclude that the Inheritance system has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurial development in South East Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Trade apprenticeship has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurial development in South East Nigeria.

Table 5: Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. An error in the Estimate		
1	.913 ^a	.834	.833	.27813		
Predictors: (Constant), APPRENTICESHIP						
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	102.038	1	102.038	1319.024	.000 ^b
	Residual	20.345	118	.077		
	Total	122.383	119			
Dependent Variable: ENTREPRENEURIAL DEVELOPMENT						
Predictors: (Constant), APPRENTICESHIP						
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.316	.110		2.864	.005
	APPRENTICESHIP	.918	.025	.913	36.318	.000
Dependent Variable: ENTREPRENEURIAL DEVELOPMENT						

Source: SPSS output 2022

The R² (Coefficient of determination): In the above model, R² = 0.834 adjusted to 0.833, which implies that approximately 84% of the variation in the dependent variable – Entrepreneurial Development is caused by the explanatory variable - Apprenticeship.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA): The F-test, which follows an F-distribution, measures the overall significance of the model. From the above result, F-Statistics was recorded (1319.024; p = 0.000) which implies that Trade apprenticeship has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurial development in South East Nigeria.

Student's T-Test: This test was conducted to ascertain the significant status of each of the parameters or variables. In doing this, we employed the two-tail tests which compared the t-calculated for the explanatory variables with the t-tabulated. The results presented in Table 5 showed “APPRENTICESHIP” ($\beta = .918$, t-cal = 36.318, p = 0.000). From the analysis, we also conclude that Trade apprenticeship has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurial development in South East Nigeria.

Discussion of Result: From the result of hypothesis 1 tested, Table 4 showed the “Inheritance System’ ($\beta = 0.854$, t-cal = 30.798, p = 0.000). From the analysis, we also conclude that the Inheritance system has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurial development in South East Nigeria. This result agreed with the result of Godwin (2020) who examined the effects of socio-cultural factors on entrepreneurial performance in selected small-scale business organizations in Bori-Ogoni. From the result of the hypothesis 2 tested; Table 5 showed “apprenticeship” ($\beta = .918$, t-cal = 36.318, p = 0.000). From the analysis, we also conclude that Trade apprenticeship has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurship development in South East Nigeria. This result agreed with the result of Ellis, Cosmas & Sussan (2019) who examined the assessment of cultural influences on the entrepreneurial activities of small

manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study adopted the survey method with an emphasis on small manufacturing firms in Nnewi. 98 manufacturing firms were sampled. The study results agreed that cultural influences affect SMEs/entrepreneurs' ability to succeed and survive. But as a note of warning, the significance of the relationship between factors of entrepreneurial success and the cultural environment should be applied with caution. Ellis, Cosmas & Sussan (2019)

Summary of Findings

This study examined the effect of Culture on Entrepreneurial Development in South East Nigeria. From the above analysis, the findings revealed that:

- I. The inheritance system has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurship development in South East Nigeria ($\beta = 0.854$, $t\text{-cal} = 30.798$, $p = 0.000$).
- II. Trade apprenticeship has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurship development in South East Nigeria ($\beta = .918$, $t\text{-cal} = 36.318$, $p = 0.000$).

Conclusion

This analysis shows that all the independent variables which are the Inheritance system, Trade apprenticeship and Language have positive and significant effects on entrepreneurship development in South East Nigeria. From the above findings, therefore, the researcher affirms that the Inheritance system has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurship development, and Trade apprenticeship has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurship development. Therefore, the study concludes that there is a positive and significant effect of culture on Entrepreneurial Development in South East Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made:

- i. The inheritance culture should be modernized to allow succession effort to thrive especially in family-owned businesses in South Eastern Nigeria, and the whole country at large. Thus, there should be good policies that will forestall the devastating effects of family in-fighting as per who inherits what, instead of stabilizing and growing the business further.
- ii. The government should partner with private organizations for a public-private-partnership (PPP) arrangement to create more modern apprenticeship schemes suited for the 21st-century economy.

Contribution to knowledge

This study to the best of the researcher's knowledge was the first to establish that the Inheritance system has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurship development in South East Nigeria. Trade apprenticeship has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurship development in South East Nigeria. The study has equally contributed to knowledge by adding to the existing literature for further studies

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